
Research

Investigate reading habit in L1 and reading habit in English among rural students at MUET

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Abstract: COVID-19 is a global epidemic for which the world was completely unprepared. It has a broad influence on a variety of facets of life. This encompasses, among other things, education, medical care, religious practice, social activities, and economic endeavors. Reading is the name of the game. Reading has an impact on one's own growth as well as the advancement of society as a whole (Sheikh & Loan, 2010). The purpose of this study is to investigate at the reading habit in L1 and reading habit in English among rural area students at MUET. The primary goal of this research is to learn more about first-year rural students' reading habit in L1 and reading habit in English. The approach follow in this study is descriptive approach. A stratified sampling strategy was used to pick 50 students who returned the survey questionnaire among 207 students at MUET. The data analysis is descriptive statistics. The findings show that students with a reading habit spend their time reading various niches that are linked to their academic as well as for enjoyment. Students with a reading habit have a detrimental effect on their reading performance.

Keywords: Reading, reading habit, rural area students.

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Introduction

COVID-19 is a pandemic disease for which the world was entirely unprepared. It has a wide-ranging impact on numerous aspects of life. This includes education, medical treatment, religious practice, social activities, and economic pursuits, among other things. It caused tremendous suffering and irreversible damage to many people in developing nations like as Nigeria, India, and Pakistan, which would take years to recover from. Governments created numerous methods to assist relieve the worrying trend, particularly during a period when the disease was on the rise geometrically. "Lockdown" is one of the several measures. This is in an attempt to halt the disease's fast spread among the population. Lockdown is simply the process of halting all activity inside a given geographic area for a set amount of time. Every aspect of human existence, including education, is impacted by Covid-19. The focus of classroom instruction has shifted to distant learning (online learning)

The name of the game is reading. Reading has an influence on one's personal development as well as society improvement in general (Sheikh & Loan, 2010). Regular and deliberate reading improves intelligence, alters attachments, heightens appetites, and broadens perspectives, Preparing a person for successful participation in social, religious, and

healing organization's (Lone, 2011). "A handicapped person has become a speaker via reading, and a crippled man has hiked heights of knowledge" (Satija, 2002). Reading enhances a person's imagination and gives the mind new perspectives and insights. Reading provides the intellect with new software (Satija, 2002).

For many people, staying at home for an extended length changes a lot of their habits and routines. Lockdown cripples nearly all activity in a state like Lagos, which is famed for its hustling and bustling. In the meanwhile, a major reduction in these activities may result in boredom and redundancy. It was stated that reading is the cornerstone of life happiness and is directly linked to professional effectiveness (Aina et al., 2011). Reading was also necessary for keeping up with the newest information or developments on the pandemic sickness or the lockdown. Reading, according to Merga (2017), is a sort of enjoyment that stimulates creativity and cognition. This means that reading provides both information and amusement in a time when both are scarce. Adolescents' reading habits are intimately linked to their emotional lexicon. Learners who read often can develop more emotional words than those who do not read frequently. Females read more digitally, according to adolescent reading habits and preferences. Academicians and parents will be better able to influence teens' reading habits if they have a better understanding of their reading patterns (Sun, 2019). According to a recent poll, the number of people who love reading during lockdown has risen from 47.8% to 55.9%. Around 35% of young adults believed that their reading habits could be improved (National literacy, 2021)

As stated by many research (Adeyemi, 2020; Mian & Chachar, 2020; Qiu et al., 2020), the World Health Organization (WHO) proclaimed the Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) a pandemic on March 12, 2020, shortly after it was reported as terminal pneumonia in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China, in December 2019. (Liu & Heinz, 2020; Noor et al., 2020). As of November 2020, 46.8 million patients have recovered from an alarming 71.6 million confirmed illnesses across 216 nations (Zhu et al., 2020). To stop the spread of the disease, a number of authorized measures were put in place. Travel restrictions, social divides, public gathering prohibitions, frequent warnings, self-exclusion, institutional confinement, preventing discomfort, curfews, and forcing individuals to stay in their houses were among them. Authorities in a number of nations have stated that curfews, lockdowns, or social isolation are necessary to prevent the spread of the infectious sickness. On the contrary, these policies had a significant impact on social security, education, tourism, and the overall functioning of countries. According to Singh and Adhikari (2020), the COVID epidemic impacted all levels of education, with schools and colleges closing indefinitely for physical education in order to minimize community engagement and prevent COVID transmission.

The initial manifestation of COVID-19 was identified in Pakistan on February 26, 2020 (Noor et al., 2020), and it swiftly progressed to the point that government authorities were compelled to bring the country to a halt on March 23, 2020 in a desperate attempt to contain COVID-19. On May 9, 2020, state authority replaced this total isolation with a smart lockdown. During this time, however, all organizations, public spaces, and educational institutions remained closed. Individuals' mental health was significantly affected by the national lockdown, social isolation, and closure of institutions, particularly among students, whose lessons were hastily moved to remote and online formats. Other issues associated to online learning, such as English reading challenges, a lack of digital skills, a lack of learning facilities, and mental stress, were brought to the fore as a result of this. Other disadvantages raised by higher education students were learning difficulties owing to a lack of face-to-face connection with instructors, slow reaction times, and a lack of typical classroom socializing. The current study was the first of its sort in Pakistan, and it looked at the influence of the epidemic on rural area first-year university students' reading habits and performance in English.

Research objectives:

- 1: To examine rural (first year) students reading habits in L1 at muet.
- 2: To examine rural (first year) students reading performance in English at muet.

Significance of study:

This research will help to provide a thorough picture of reading habits among rural first-year university students in Pakistan, as well as their link with performance reading in English at MUET. It explains how reading plays a part in

higher education. The current study will raise awareness of rural university students' reading habits, as well as the link between their reading habits and their English reading performance. As a result, educators, policymakers, curriculum designers, instructors, students, and parents will benefit from the present research.

Research methodology:

This is a quantitative study since it relied on a survey research approach to establish demographic claims. In quantitative research, survey research designs are methods in which investigators give a survey to a sample or the full population of individuals in order to characterize the population's views, beliefs, behaviors, or attributes (Creswell, 2012). Quantitative research is described as a systematic analysis of phenomena through the collection of measurable data and the use of statistical, mathematical, or computational methods. Quantitative research gathers data from current and future consumers by employing sampling methods and sending out online surveys, polls, questionnaires, and other forms of data collection, the results of which may be represented numerically. After gaining a thorough grasp of these figures, you may forecast the future of a product or service and make modifications as needed.

Sampling and Participants:

In the present study's sample is stratified because this sampling methodology divides the entire population into subpopulations and this way of sampling characteristics is based on gender, race, and other factors. Rural first-year students at MUET are essential participants in this study.

Participants are chosen from MUET's several Engineering departments. Students are chosen from these departments depending on their rural location. A total of 50 students from the Engineering department's first year would be chosen for this study.

Reliability and validity:

The dependability of a construct's calculation is defined as the magnitude under which it is trustworthy. A pilot study will be undertaken before the main study in this research. The pilot study is being conducted to aid in the accuracy of research tools for the main study. Also, the internal accuracy reliability of this study is based on assessing the questionnaire's reliability, and the reading test will be tested using Spss and the Cronbach alpha value.

Instrument:

This study necessitated the assessment of a large group of people's reading habits in English, in their first language, and all together. The purpose of employing a survey questionnaire is to draw attention to the fact that one exists. The Skendari 2017 reading habit questionnaire was used for this investigation.

Findings:

For first-year students in rural settings, all 19 questions have a minimum Bach's alpha value of ($=\alpha .941$). For first-year rural students in English and in L1 reading habits, the mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) of each question were determined based on the replies of all participants.

Table no 1 Descriptive statistics of Reading habit in L1

		Statistics						
		Magazine	Literature	Novel	Poetry	History	Newspaper	Textbook
N	Valid	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.2800	3.5800	3.5600	3.6200	3.8000	3.4200	2.2200
Median		2.0000	4.0000	3.0000	4.0000	3.0000	4.0000	2.0000
Std. Deviation		1.03095	1.60471	1.51402	1.93665	1.71429	1.51307	1.16567

Table 1 showed reading habit in L1 of rural area students at MUET. Median in this table is show the preference of participants that rural students read literature and poetry, newspaper twice weekly basis and novel and history on monthly basis. Also, magazine reading , textbook on rarely basis.

Table 02 Descriptive statistics of reading habit in English

		Statistics						
		Magazine	Literature	Novel	Poetry	History	Newspaper	Textbook
N	Valid	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		4.3600	3.8000	3.2200	2.8400	3.9200	3.9800	3.4000
Median		5.0000	3.0000	3.0000	3.0000	4.0000	4.0000	3.0000
Std. Deviation		1.74683	1.97949	1.68171	1.54339	1.46858	1.44970	1.38505

This table shows that novel was in moderate high range while reading in low range. This table shows that first column describes Mean, median and St. Deviation. From second to last column describe reading in English. Because the data was not normally distributed, the row for median is the most essential because a higher median in a question suggests that respondents choose that specific material. Respondents most frequently read magazine in English (Mdn 5) which is weekly than history and newspaper. The lowest frequently read Genre was (Mdn 3) monthly basis.

Result and discussion:

Participants' poor reading habits in L2 learning, excluding text book reading in English, were shown by the data analysis. Similarly, participants in L1 learning had reading habits, aside from text book and newspaper reading in Linguistic knowledge, and students' reading habits in English and L1 were different in first-year students. Students in urban regions indicate that they have all of the conveniences they need at home, so they spend their time either playing computer games or going outside and participating in outdoor activities with their friends. Participants' poor reading habits in L2 learning, excluding text book reading in English, were shown in one quantitative investigation. Similarly, participants in L1 learning had poor reading habits, except from text book and newspaper reading in Linguistic knowledge, and students' reading habits in English and L1 were dissimilar in urban first-year students. Participants in the research were not used to reading and said they read mostly for exams, professional development, and improving their spoken and written English abilities. The participants study their notes and look for information on the internet (Diwan, 2020). According to another study, individuals' reading habits had an impact on educational achievements. Furthermore, it has been shown that the practice of reading may have served as a conduit for gaining world consciousness. (2019, Kumara)

Recommendation:

The researchers advise pupils to develop a reading interest in English reading materials, given the importance of reading. In this modern era, when most of one's time is spent at home, it's a good idea to start formulating and developing reading activities on English materials, and to make it a habit in everyday life, not only in English classes. It is also recommended that teachers train their pupils to build their reading habits across a variety of text genres. Reading will be more meaningful and useful, according to Cambria and Guthrie (2010), if the reading interest that precedes the reading is founded in one's intrinsic desire rather than the power of other arts or extrinsic incentives. According to Pakistan's education policymakers, a monolingual approach should be replaced with a trans language and bilingual approach (Al-Ahdal, 2020), which begins with exposure to speaking skills and progresses to other skills,

ensuring that learners' proficiency in English, also known as the library language, is improved. It is intended that, in the long term, these techniques would prepare Pakistani students to engage in self-paced, self-directed autonomous learning and to compete in the knowledge world to enhance its economic sectors. Bangladesh has lately developed a way to significantly improve the country's infrastructure. As part of this purpose, the government has invested a positive.

References

- [1] Adeyemi, I. O. (2020). Influence of Covid-19 Lockdown on Reading Habit of Nigerians: A Case Study of Lagos State Inhabitants. *Reading and Writing Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10573569.2020.1857891>
- [2] Al-Ahdal, A. A. M. H. (2020). Translanguagism and the bilingual EFL learner of Saudi Arabia: Exploring new vistas. *Asian EFL Journal*, vol. 27(1), 14-26
- [3] Aina, A. J., Ogungbeni, J. I., Adigun, J. A., & Ogundipe, T. C. (2011). Poor reading habits among Nigerians: The roles of libraries. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal), 529. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/529>
- [4] Bolatov, A. K., Seisembekov, T. Z., Askarova, A. Z., Baikanova, R. K., Smailova, D. S., & Fabbro, E. (2020). Online-Learning due to COVID-19 Improved Mental Health Among Medical Students. *Medical Science Educator*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40670-020-01165-y>
- [5] Cheng et al., (1997). An investigation of public high school EFL teachers' habits of reading for professional growth. Proceedings of the Fourteenth Conference on English Teaching and Learning in the Republic of China. pp.107-117. Taipei: *The Crane Publishing Co., Ltd.*
- [6] Farooq, F., Rathore, F. A., & Mansoor, S. N. (2020). Challenges of online medical education in Pakistan during COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan*, 30(1), S67–S69. <https://doi.org/10.29271/jcpsp.2020.Supp1.S67>
- [7] Huang, SHua., Capps, M., Blacklock, J., & Garza, M. (2014). Reading habits of college students in the United States. *Reading Psychology*, 35(5), 437–467. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/02702711.2012.739593>
- [8] Kaur, A. P., & Ghuman, S. S. (2019). Reading Habits of Postgraduate Students of Khalsa College, Amritsar: A Survey. *KIIT Journal of Library and Information Management*, 6(2), 121. <https://doi.org/10.5958/2455-8060.2019.00017.x>
- [9] Khatoon, S., Abidin, M. J. Z., Mirza, Q., & Hussain, A. (2020). Blogging in esl class-gender-based attitude of the engineering students. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 9(4), 1128–1137. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v9i4.20673>
- [10] Lone, F. A. (2011). Reading Habits of Rural and Urban College Students in the 21st Century. *Library philosophy and practice journal*.

